

A comment to improve tumor treating fields therapy

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Abstract:

Recent investigations have shown that special frequencies and intensities of electromagnetic waves could control differentiations of some types of cells. Using this fact, tumor-treating fields (TTFields) therapy is proposed as a technique which uses alternating electric fields of intermediate frequency (~100-500 kHz) and low intensity (1-3 V/cm) to disrupt cell divisions of tumors. However, this technique may have harmful effects on ionic liquids around normal cells. For example, electrodes could induce an extra electrical currents within blood vessels. To observe these effects, we connect electrodes to a slide including water and some extra ions and put them under a 1000x microscope. We find that 1. Some ions, microbes and cells are moving towards negative electrodes and some go away. These attractions of cells by electrodes could cause to destruction of a brain. 2. Some electrical currents within liquid are emerged which absorb or repel water molecules and induce some bubbles. If these types of bubbles are emerged within the blood vessels, they can force on the membranes of normal cells and destroy them. To avoid these problems, we suggest to replace electrodes by some electromagnetic sender/receivers which emit some special frequencies. These frequencies could be taken only by blood vessels around tumors. Because, these vessels may be created only to provide needed food of tumor cells and thus, have different potential and electrical current respect to vessels around normal cells. Thus, these tumor vessels could act as the antenna for TTFields.

I.Introduction

One of best electromagnetic field therapy methods is the tumor treating fields (TTFields), which applies the low-intensity, intermediate frequency electrical fields to treat tumors.[1-5] The generating device of this technique has been built by the Novocure and was approved in the United States and Europe for the treatment of newly diagnosed and recurrent glioblastoma

multiforme (GBM), and was undergoing clinical trials for several other cancer types .[6,7]

Up to date, many investigations have been done on this therapy technique. For example, a paper has studied the macroscopic spatial distribution of TTFields generated in the human head, and of the microscopic field distribution in tumor cells. In addition, preclinical and clinical findings related to TTFields and principles of its operation were considered.[8] In other study, authors evaluated whether TTFields-mediated cell death can elicit antitumoral immunity and hence would be effectively combined with anti-PD-1 therapy.[9]

In other work, authors have considered whether TTFields effected the regulation of autophagy in glioma cells. They found that autophagy is upregulated in glioma cells treated with TTFields as demonstrated by immunoblot analysis of the lipidated microtubule-associated protein light chain 3 (LC3-II).[10] Another group quantified Optune's duty cycle and predicted the steady-state temperature distribution in the head during GBM treatment.[11] Some other authors provided an assessment of possible physical interactions between 100 kHz range alternating electric fields and biological cells in general and their nano-scale subcellular structures in particular.[12]

In all of these investigations, electrodes have been located on the scalp. Thus, much values of currents pass through healthy cells and may destruct their membranes. We will show this by connecting electrodes to a slid including ionic liquid under a microscope. We will observe induction of non desired bubbles which could explode and vanish cells. To avoid this problem, we suggest long distance radiations. These radiations should pass the normal cells and produce needed voltage and frequency within liquids or blood vessels around tumor cells.

In section II, we propose the method for considering effects of electrodes on ionic liquid. In section III, we show the results of experiment. In section IV, we discuss and propose a new TTField therapy technique which has no these harmful effects. The last section is devoted to conclusion.

III. Materials and method

In this section, we will show that electrodes on the scalp, induce some electrical currents within blood vessels of a brain. This is because that blood liquid includes ions and hemoglobin molecules. These molecules contain iron atoms which could act as the transmitter of waves and electrons or electrical currents. These currents could absorb or repel other molecules and produce some bubbles within the liquid. These bubbles could explode and vanish normal cells (See Figure 1). To observe these events, we need to connect a slide of ionic liquids to some electrodes and put it under a microscope (See Figure 2).

Details of materials and method are:

III-A: Materials:

Materials of experiment are:

Microscope, Electrodes, Generator, Water, Oil, blood or other ionic liquid, wires, camera, milk, a sample of microbes

III-B: Methods

First: we connect some electrodes to a generator which produce voltages and frequencies closed to applied voltage and frequency in TTFIELD technique.

Second: We connect electrodes to a slide which its sized be bigger of normal slides and could bear the electrical currents related to electrodes. We put 1-3 millimeter distances between matters on the slide and electrodes.

Third: we mix water with some ionic liquids. Blood is a very good case, however, one can use of a mixture of oil and water . or a mixture of milk and water.

Fourth: We build a sample of microbes within liquids

Fifth: We put slide under a microscope and turn on generator. We take some videos of evolutions within the liquids.

Figure 1. Emergence of non desired electrical current within blood vessels during TTField therapy

Figure 2. Induction of bubbles within liquid by connecting electrodes to a slide of ionic liquid.

III. Results:

In this section, we will bring some observations of induction of harmful bubbles by electrodes.

In figure 3, we observe that microbes and ionic molecules are collected near an electrode. It is because that most microbes and biological cells have charged particles on their membranes and could be attracted or repelled by electrodes. The same event may be occurred within the brain. Some cells could be more attracted and some less and some distributions or destructions within the brain occurs.

In figure 4, we add some ions and charged particles to water and turn on generator. It is clear that electrical currents produce many bubbles such as microbes could be seen less. Maybe, microbes disappear by electrical currents and bubbles.

In figure 5, again, we repeat the experiment by using a sample of molecules and microbes which are appeared within the milk. Before turning on the generator, microbes and other molecules are in their natural size.

In figure 6, we turn on the generator. Some ionic molecules are excited and grow. They move and cause to excitation and growth of other molecules and even microbes. The same event may occur within the brain and by using electrodes, some cells may grow. Because, membranes are formed from charged particles and could be affected by electrodes.

In figure 7, we put approximately pure water under the microscope and turn on generator. By passing time, some bubbles are emerged. These bubbles are small at first.

In figure 8, we observe that small bubbles grow and become big. These big bubbles could destroy the structure of cells. This event may be the main harmful effect of electrodes in TTFIELD therapy method.

In figure 9. we observe that by passing time, not only bubbles become very big, but number of microbes grow. Because, microbes, accept new conditions and eventually, they use of new electrical cycle and obtain needed temperature and energy for growth.

Figure 3. Attraction of microbes and ions by electrodes and electrical currents

Figure 4. Emergence of many bubbles and disappearing microbes by connecting slide to electrodes. Liquid is separated from electrodes, however, its effects could be observed.

Figure 5: A sample of molecules and microbes within a water+milk before turning on generator

Figure 6. Effect of electrodes on size of molecules and microbes after turning on the generator

Figure 7. Emergence of small bubbles within a pure water connected to electrodes. Electrodes have 1-3 millimeter separation distances from the liquid.

Figure 8. Growth of bubbles within a pure water during electrode radiation.

Figure 9. Growth of bubbles and increase of number of microbes within a liquid by electrode radiation.

IV. Discussion

Above results show that electrode radiation could cause to many harmful effects on blood and also normal cells. To avoid of these problems, we can use of large distant sources. It has been know that tumor cells have different radiation and structures respect to normal cells. Specially, some tumors form new blood vessels to provide their food. Each blood vessel contains many hemoglobin and ions. Each hemoglobin molecule contain some iron atoms. These iron atoms could act like the antenna and receive electromagnetic waves. By using these molecules and differences between blood vessels around tumor and normal cells, we can design a sender which emit some special electromagnetic waves and these waves could be taken by molecules within tumor blood vessels. These waves induce needed frequency and voltage around tumor cells (See Figure 10).

Figure 10. Replacing electrodes by distant electromagnetic sources and induction of needed voltages around tumors by using differences between blood vessels around tumor and normal cells.

Conclusions

Up to date, it has been known that TTFIELDS therapy is one of the best medical methods in curing tumors. However, in this research, we have shown that electrodes on the scalp could induce some electrical currents within the blood vessels and other liquids around normal cells. These currents could cause the emergence of some big bubbles which force the structure of cells and destroy it. We have suggested that electrodes be replaced by some electromagnetic senders/receivers. These senders emit some special waves which are taken up by blood vessels around tumors and produce the needed voltage and frequencies.

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